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OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Deliverables 5.2 / 5.3

Graph search / Dashboard

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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Editor	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)				
Work Programme Description	<p>Deliverable 5.2 Graph search. Integrating the three existing environments' databases using semantic technologies. It includes modelling their databases using OWL and transforming their contents to RDF. New interfaces –based on the existing Oikontology prototype– will be created to facilitate the knowledge modelling and reuse by different types of users: domain experts in the fields of housing, learning designers and students. The interfaces will provide functionalities to make explicit links between elements from the knowledge generated at the different project areas, in particular by the three subnetworks.</p> <p>Deliverable 5.3 Dashboard. The activities of the network will be dynamically captured and brought to the dashboard which will be accessible at the homepage of the network portal. The information will be presented in multiple forms: Visual maps, flow charts, graph representations, and classical reports. Implementation of methods to introduce the log of the activities carried out outside the learning environments such as face to face workshops.</p>				
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the work done in Deliverable 5.2 “Graph Search” and Deliverable 5.3 “Dashboard”, two of the components of the OIKONET Digital Platform presented in Deliverable 5.1. As originally described in the work programme, the Graph Search and Dashboard were planned as independent tools that would be accessible from the home page. As a result of the work carried out during the project, we have come to the conclusion that the web portal, the graph search and the dashboard should be constituent components of a unique semantic-based information system. These two components -Oikonetwork (i.e. a graph search tool) and Dashboard- are fully integrated in the digital platform and jointly described in this document.

The OIKONET web portal is a semantic-based information system in which the information is introduced in the semantic data repository (i.e. a triple store) by means of dynamic forms that respond to the vocabulary of the project (e.g. learning spaces, workshops, exhibitions, conferences, meetings, etc.). To create these forms, it has been necessary to develop first a set of tools to enable an expert user to create forms for each category of information recognized in the system’s ontology. In particular, five tools have been created:

- A “vocabulary tool” that enables reusing ontologies used by a community of users.
- A “dynamic form tool” to create semantic structures using visual forms.
- A “search tool” helps to manage the contents introduced using the dynamic form tool.
- A “share tool” to explore the internal structure of the data
- An API to facilitate remote access to the repository.

These tools enable the creation of forms to introduce in the semantic system a particular element of information (e.g. news, workshops, conferences, meetings), including its relationships to other elements of the system. Through these ad-hoc forms, an advanced user can feed the system with the information about the project activities facilitated by different means (reports, email communications, shared documents in the cloud).

The semantically structured data can be later displayed in multiple ways in the web portal:

- in the dynamic contents of a page in the OIKONET web portal
- in the dashboard (home page of the OIKONET web portal, view list)
- in a visual graph (visual map in the Oikonetwork environment)

The visual graph has its own environment named Oikonetwork. Within this environment, users can navigate from one node to another, retrieving the items associated to each node (e.g. reports, images, videos). Besides, users can seamlessly navigate between the two visualization modes, from the web pages to the visual graph.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This is a technical report of the tools developed in Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3. The target groups are experts in the field of semantic information systems, semantic data modelling and graph search tools.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The tools described in this report have been conceived and implemented by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle (FUNITEC), leader of WP5 Digital Platform. Other partners have collaborated providing their feedback to the different versions of the Oikonetwork environment that have been produced during its development.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

All project activities are captured by the semantic information system. The semantically modelled data enable partners and external users to have an easy access to the project activities and results.

3 PLATFORM INTEGRATION

3.1 Web portal, Graph Search and Dashboard

As originally described in the work programme, the Graph Search and Dashboard were planned as independent tools that would be accessible from the home page. As a result of the work carried out during the project, we have come to the conclusion that the Web portal, the graph search and the dashboard should be constituent components of a unique semantic-based information system. This concept of a unified information system that provides access to the activities generated by the network and enables its visualization in multiples ways (as graph, as dashboard) was not mature enough at the moment of writing the proposal; rather, it has been the result of the work carried out in the project. For this reason, the Graph Search and Dashboard are jointly described in this report, which complements the description of the OIKONET Digital Platform presented in Deliverable 5.1 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of the OIKONET Digital Platform

The OIKONET web portal (see Deliverable 5.1) is a semantic-based information system in which the information is introduced by means of dynamic forms that respond to the vocabulary of the project (e.g. learning spaces, workshops, exhibitions, conferences, meetings, etc.). These forms are used to input information about a particular project activity (e.g. the name and description of a workshop) as well as about the relationships to other information items (e.g. the participating partners, the documents produced) recognized in the system's ontology. In this way, the information is introduced only once through these forms and then visualized in multiple ways in the web portal (Figure 2):

- in the dynamic contents of a page in the web portal
- in the Dashboard (home page of the web portal, view list)
- in the Graph Search tool (visual map in the OIKONETWORK environment)

Figure 2. Inputs and outputs of the semantic information system

4 SEMANTIC DATA REPOSITORY TOOLS

This section describes the development of the tools which are necessary to semantically model the information generated during the project. These tools have been specifically created for the OIKONET web portal. This has implied the creation of a Semantic Data Repository which includes the forms necessary to introduce information according to the system’s ontology. The semantically modelled data is visualized on the web portal as well as in OIKONETWORK, a graph search tool which enables users to access the information by means of interactive visual maps.

The objective of the Semantic Data Repository is to enable users, without knowledge about semantic technologies, to model data semantically. It consists of the following tools:

- A “vocabulary tool” that enables reusing ontologies used by a community of users
- A “dynamic form tool” to create semantic structures using visual forms
- A “search tool” helps to manage the contents introduced using the dynamic form tool
- A “share tool” to explore the internal structure of the data
- An API to facilitate remote access to the repository

In the next sections, tools that make the Semantic Data Repository are described.

4.1.1 Vocabulary tool

The vocabulary tool is used to add to the repository existing ontologies that suit to the data to be modelled. In the case of the OIKONET project, these are ontologies which might refer to the description of an organization, to a publication, or to an event, among other. With this tool, the classes and properties of existing vocabularies are used to create the dynamic forms used to introduce the information in the repository.

Name	Url	Show	Add
OIKONET	http://www.oikonet.org/ontology/	Show	Add
Oikodemos Workspaces	http://www.oikodemos.org/oiko/workspace.owl	Show	X
Oikodemos Oikopedia	http://www.oikodemos.org/oiko/oikopedia.owl	Show	X
Oikodemos Caserepository	http://www.oikodemos.org/oiko/caserepository.owl	Show	X
DCMI	http://purl.org/dc/terms/	Show	X
FOAF	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/	Show	X
BIBO	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/structuredynamics/Bibliographic-Ontology-BIBO/master/bibo.xml.owl	Show	X

Figure 3. Interface of the vocabulary tool

In the tool interface (Figure 3), the option “Show” is used to display the classes, properties and other details contained in the selected vocabulary. The option “X” is used to delete the vocabulary. A vocabulary that has been deleted is no longer available for creating new forms. However, deleting it does not affect the already created ones.

The “Add vocabulary” tool consists of two fields (Figure 4): a name to identify the vocabulary

and the URL of the file that contains it. This file needs to be in RDF format. Typically, the URL corresponds to the first part of the URI classes. The vocabulary can be previewed before stored.

Figure 4. Add vocabulary form

At the start of the vocabulary list, a special vocabulary can be found (in Figure 3 named OIKONET). The objective of this vocabulary is to enable the addition of independent properties if the user does not find the exact meaning in the already created vocabularies. This prevents from creating a new vocabulary only for one property and thus avoids overloading the Semantic Data Repository with unused properties. Although RDF and OWL enable to relate several annotation properties when a new property is added to a vocabulary (e.g. description of the property, author, date of creation), this tool only requires a name and a description to facilitate the aggregation of new data (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Add property form

4.1.2 Dynamic form tool

The dynamic form tool is used to create an input interface to introduce the data and their relationships into the information system. These forms contain the new concepts and their data as triple stores. A semantic structure is determined transparently to the user during the creation of the dynamic form. All the dynamic forms are shown in a list, each entry having three options: add data to the form, modify its structure, and delete the form (Figure 6). Modifying and deleting a form do not alter the information previously added. For example, if in the form “Book” the field ISBN is deleted, the new instances of this class will not have an ISBN; instead the old book instances will retain the one they have.

HOME VOCABULATY **FORM** SEARCH EndpointData SparqlEndpoint

Forms
[create new](#)

Name	Base in			
Activity	Event	Add data		
Conference	Conference	Add data		
Deliverable	Student Work	Add data		
Document	Document	Add data		
Events	Event	Add data		
Image	Image	Add data		
Learning space	Workspace	Add data		
Meetings	Event	Add data		

Figure 6. Dynamic Form Tool

Clicking on “Create new” opens a dialogue box to create dynamic forms. This dialogue box divided into two main areas (Figure 7). The upper part of the form contains the following fields:

- *Form name*: Name used to identify the new dynamic form
- *Based in class*: Class used to define the semantic meaning of the form, this is important if the user wants to export the data
- *Properties related to the class*: Properties list box to add a field to the new dynamic form. Only the properties related to the selected class appear in the list box. More than one property can be added
- *All properties*: The same as the previous field, but the list box contains all the vocabularies properties
- *Search Properties*: It is used to search for properties using a part of the name

Figure 7. New Dynamic Form

The lower part of the dialogue box (in grey background), contains all the properties included in the previous section. It has the following fields:

- *Name*: It is the field name. By default, it is the name of the property but this can be changed.
- *Required*: It is used to specify whether the field is compulsory or not.
- *Type*: It is used to select the type of field.
 - *SimpleText*: a simple input text without options.
 - *TextEditor*: a text area with styles options.
 - *Date*: an input date chosen by date picker
 - *File*: an input upload file
 - *Image*: an input upload file that will be shown as image
 - *Relation*: a selection box that make a relation with another form (1-1)
 - *MultipleRelations*: a selection box to set a relation with another form (1-N)
 - *Size*: it is used to select the width of the field
 - *Related*: It is used to choose the foreign key of the form. It is only enabled if the type is Relation or MultipleRelation

Once a form has been created, the user can start filling it to create the objects or elements that form represents (i.e. its instances). Each form will have a different visualization depending on how it was created. An example is shown in Figure 8. At the top of the page, there is the control “Click to get Link to [Name] form”. The user clicks here to get a link to access directly the form. It is used to share the form with other users who need to add new instances. Next, it is the name of the form, “Activity”, and the base class, “Event”. Finally, the fields that will contain the data in the form are facilitated. For example, Figure 8 shows a dynamic form that has a title of a property that is a “SimpleText”, the content that is a “TextEditor”, date created that is a “Date” and source that is a “MultipleRelations”.

HOME VOCABULATY **FORM** SEARCH EndpointData SparqlEndpoint

Click to get Link to the Activity form:

Activity form (Event)

title

content

File Edit Insert View Format Table Tools

Formats B I U

☰ ☰ ☰ ☰

☰ ☰ ☰ ☰

A A

p Words: 0

date created

source

- Lisbon_Workskhop_A3poster
- Lisbon_Workskhop_programe
- Lisbon Workskhop A3poster
- Lisbon Workskhop programme

Figure 8. Dynamic form example

4.1.3 Search tool

The search tool is used to have access to the contents introduced using the forms that are part of the Semantic Data Repository. When the search tool is invoked, the last twelve added instances are shown (Figure 9). The user can modify the searching criteria using two search options:

- “*Get all instances of the form*” which returns all the instances that match with the selected dynamic form
- “*Search type*” which has four additional options:
 - *Class*: The written string tries to match one class name. It returns all the forms and its instances that use the class to give semantic meaning
 - *Form*: The written string tries to match with the name of the form and returns all the instances of this form
 - *Property*: The written string tries to match a property name and returns all instances forms that use this property
 - *Value*: The written string tries to match the value of the properties of each instance and returns the instances that have that value

The user can edit and delete the retrieved instances clicking on the icons next to their headers.

Figure 9. Search tool

4.1.4 Share tool

The share tool consists of two interfaces. The first interface displays all triples stored in the repository in a table (Figure 10). This helps users, with no knowledge about the Semantic Web, to explore the internal structure of the information stored in the information system. These triples can be downloaded into a file to export the database content.

Subject	Predicate	Object
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#formulary>	<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>	<http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Class>
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#formulary>	<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label>	"formulary"
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#instance>	<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>	<http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Class>
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#instance>	<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label>	"instance"
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#hasType>	<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>	<http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#ObjectProperty>
<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#hasType>	<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#domain>	<http://www.oikonet.org/ontology#formulary>

Figure 10. Endpoint data

The second interface is an SPARQL endpoint that enables a user with knowledge about SPARQL to make queries to examine the internal structure of the semantic data (Figure 11). The interface includes a filter to query the different types of semantic data available in the semantic data repository. The possible choices for the filter are: data (i.e. data introduced with the forms, and vocabularies (i.e. terms used for creating the forms)

Figure 11. SPARQL Endpoint

4.1.5 API tool

An API tool provides a set of functionalities that remote applications can use to get data in JSON format or to add new data. These functionalities are the following:

- *addInstance*: Add to the repository a new instance of an already created form
- *sendFormInstances*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with all the instances of the given name form
- *sendInstanceList*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with all the names and creation data of the instances of the given name form
- *sendInstanceFilterList*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with list of instances of the given name form that have a relation to a given instance. It only returns name and date
- *sendFormListRelatedTo*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with all the forms related to another form
- *sendLastInstances*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with the last instances of the given form subset
- *sendInstance*: Retrieve from the repository a JSON variable with a specific instance

4.2 Introducing information using the semantic data repository tools

This section describes the process of introducing the information that is being generated in the OIKONET project using the forms created with the tools described in the previous section. Through these forms, the information is structured in categories (e.g. news, workshops, conferences, meetings) and stored in the semantic data repository along with the relations to other elements of information. The information stored can be later displayed in multiple ways on the web portal (in the dynamic pages, in the dashboard, and in the visual graph).

In the process of introducing information in the semantic data repository there are three kinds of users involved:

- *Contributor*: a generator of information, a user that produces information, usually a partner that attends meetings, produces documents, participates in workshops.
- *Administrator*: an advanced user that creates the forms for introducing the information. The Administrator has technical knowledge to work with the semantic data repository tools.
- *Editor*: a user who introduces the information produced by the Contributors using the forms created by the Administrators.

Some of the information generated by the project is registered by partners in a set of shared documents stored in Google Drive. The information provided by these shared documents are the starting point in the process of creating the semantic data repository using the forms.

To introduce a new element in the semantic information system (e.g. a document), the first step is to determine the type of the element and its attributes. Using the dynamic form tool of the semantic data repository, a form is created describing a specific element and its properties. The type of the properties can be, for example, a text, a date, a file, an image, and relations to

other elements. Once the form is created, the element can be introduced in the system by filling in the form.

The following example (Figure 12) shows how the structure of the Google doc shared document “Project Meetings Log” have been mapped to the form “Meetings”.

Figure 12. Mapping information from a shared document onto a form

The elements of information generated within the project, are related to other elements. Therefore, the forms include not only the information specific to a certain element but also the relations held with other elements. For example, a meeting has its own attributes such as the venue and date. But a meeting is related to other elements of information such as the partners which attended the meeting and the documents that were generated, like minutes and presentations. Accordingly, the process to fill in the information in a form is the following: first, to introduce the items that are specific to the element such as images, documents and partners among others; and, second, to introduce the relations to other elements (e.g. meetings and news).

For example, for introducing a meeting (e.g. “Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy”) the forms “Meeting” and “Document” are used. The information about the meeting is stored in a spreadsheet shared by all the consortium partners (Figure 13). The content of the spreadsheet is introduced in the semantic repository by means of the forms.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
9	P12-UL	Research	Second meeting of the subnetwork	16/06/2014	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Leandro Madrazo, Karim Hadji, Isalah Diuremi Durosaye, Lasse Fryk, Maartje van Eerd (IHS), Gojko Bezovan, Sašo Medved, Suzana Domjan, Viggo Nordvik, Adrienne Csizmady, Gábor Csánádi, Nadia Charatambous (via Skype), Leandro Madrazo (la.salle), Roberto Ricci (OAPPCR), Raúl Robert (SostreCivic), Filippo Boschi, Valentina Ridolfi, Simona Rotteglia (Heriscape), Daniela Nagyova, Monika Smirnova (Bratislava Municipality), Simona Leandro Madrazo (Project coordinator, WP4 leader), Angel Martin	https://www.dropbox.com/home/OIKONET/CONSO.../WP4_RESEARCH/MEETINGS/MEETING_2_Ljubljana
10	P11-OAPPCR	Community	Second meeting of the subnetwork	27/06/2014	Rimini, Italy	Carla Sentier, Rafael López Gallego, Viera Joklova, Marian Malovany, Tomas Ooms,	https://www.dropbox.com/home/OIKONET/CONSO.../WP4_COMMUNITY/MEETINGS/MEETING_3_Rimini
11	P25-ISCTE	Pedagogy	Second meeting of the subnetwork	7/15/2014-7/17/2014	Lisbon, Portugal	Carla Sentier, Rafael López, Viera Joklova, Henrich Pirko, Johan Verbeke, Tomas Ooms,	https://www.dropbox.com/home/OIKONET/CONSO.../WP4_PEDAGOGY/MEETINGS/MEETING_4_Lisbon
12	P1-FUNITEC	Project	General meeting 1	9/25/2014-9/27/2014	Barcelona, Spain	Lukas Staudinger, Anna Picco-Schwendener, (Zaimers), Ellen Geurts (IHS), Sašo ana Domjan(UL), ars (RTU), Gojko Bezovan, Josip PFI, Adrienne Csizmady,	https://www.dropbox.com/home/OIKONET/CONSO.../WP4_PROJECT/MEETINGS/MEETING_5_Barcelona
13	P1-FUNITEC	Research	Third meeting of the subnetwork			Henrich Pirko (IASTU), Tomas Ooms (KU Leuven), Mathias Kloeppel (BTU), Anna Picco-Schwendener, Stefano Tardin (USI), Vasilija Trova (UTH), Nicolai Steina (GAU), Elna Pattichi (LUCY), Adriana Diaconu (LIPFM, via Skype) Sedef Ozealik (GYTE),	
14	P1-FUNITEC	Pedagogy	Third meeting of the subnetwork	30/01/2015	Istanbul, Turkey	Henrich Pirko (IASTU), Minsjo Zinsko (UKIM), Pietro Cesari (OAPPCR), Raúl Robert (SostreCivic), Dorina Papa (POLIS), Simona Rotteglia (HERISCAPE) Anton Gabor,	
15	P1-FUNITEC	Community	Third meeting of the subnetwork		Bratislava, Slovakia		

Figure 13. Shared spreadsheet to record project meetings (Google docs)

This is another example. With the occasion of the “Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy”, several documents have been produced which are introduced with the form “Document” (Figure 14). This form has the following attributes: title, source, link, video and a relation to a member element.

The screenshot shows the OIKONET web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'VOCABULATY', 'FORM', 'SEARCH', 'EndpointData', and 'SparqlEndpoint'. Below this, a message says 'Click to get Link to the Document form:'. The main form is titled 'Document form (Document)'. It contains the following fields:

- title:** WP4_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Viera Joklova_He
- source:** A dropdown menu with 'Examinar...' selected and the text 'No se ha seleccionado ningún archivo.'
- link:** A text input field with 'Insert link' placeholder.
- video:** A text input field with 'Insert video' placeholder.
- member:** A dropdown menu with a list of names: 'Cjirka', 'Hadida', 'Hadji', 'Hannula', 'Joklova' (highlighted in blue), 'Kalauzis', 'Klöpfel', 'Krasilnikova', 'Kühn', 'Kuzina', 'Lalanda'.

 At the bottom of the form is a 'Modify Document' button.

Figure 14. Document form

After the documents have been introduced in the semantic data repository, the meeting element is introduced using the meeting form (Figure 15). The form is filled using the data from the “Project Meetings Log” shared document. The attributes “Participants” and “Reference

documents” take more than one item. Those attributes are used to relate the meeting element to the document elements previously introduced.

13	P1-FUNITEC	Research	Third meeting of the subnetwork	Budapest, Hungary	Medved, Suzana Domjan(IUL), Edgers Bonders (RTU), Gojko Bezover, Josip Pandzic (ISF/PFZ), Adrienne Cizmady,
14	P1-FUNITEC	Pedagogy	Third meeting of the subnetwork	30/01/2015 Istanbul, Turkey	Carla Sentieri (ETSA_PV), Henrich Pitko (PASTU), Tomas Ooms (KU Leuven), Mathias Kioepfel (ETU), Anna Picco-Schwendener, Stefano Tardin (USI), Vassilia Trova (UTH), Nicolas Steina (AAU), Elina Paticchi (LACY), Adriana Diaconu (LRFM, via Skype) Sedef Ozcecik (GYTE),
15	P1-FUNITEC	Com			Mihajlo Zindski (UKM), Mihajlo Zindski (UKM),

The screenshot shows the OIKONET web portal interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: HOME, VOCABULARY, FORMS, SEARCH, EndpointData, and Reports. Below the navigation, there is a section titled 'Click to get Link to the Meetings form:'. The 'Meetings form (Event)' is displayed with the following fields:

- Name: Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy
- start date: 30-01-2015
- end date: 30-01-2015
- Place: Istanbul
- Participants: A list of names including Nordvik, Ouremi Durosaye, Denis, Olovik Guney, Pajo, Picco-Schwendener, Pajo, Paj, Pajuguelis, and Ramon.
- organizer: A list of institutions including HENTSCAPE, HSUB, IHS, ISCTE, ITU, KU_LEUVEN, LASALLE, NOVA, OAPPCR, PFZ, and PASTU.
- Deliverable: A list of documents including Quality management plan, Readings on contemporary housing research, Report on participatory actions, Second year report, Social web, Subnetwork Meetings - WP3, Subnetwork Meetings - WP1, Subnetwork Meetings - WP2, and Third year report.
- Reference documents: A list of document titles including WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Learning space, Adriana Diaconu, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Andrej Tokajuk, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Leandro Madraco, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Vera Jokova, Henrich Pitko, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Stefano Tardin, Anna Picco-Schwendener, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Leandro Madraco, Angel Martin, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Housing Systems, Leandro Madraco, Angel Martin, WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Alexandra Pais, and WPI_MEETING3_INSTANBUL_Carla Sentieri.

At the bottom of the form, there is a 'Modify Meetings' button and a footer note: 'This project is funded with support from the European Commission (Project number: 53309-LLP1-2015-1-ES-ERASMUS). This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.'

Figure 15. Taking the information from the Google doc into the semantic data repository

Once all the elements have been introduced in the semantic data repository, they are accessible to the OIKONET Digital platform components, in particular to the Web portal, Dashboard and OIKONETWORK. In each component, the information is displayed in different ways based on the data registered through the OIKONET forms (Figure 16).

The image displays two screenshots from the OIKONET project website. The left screenshot is the 'Web Portal' for the 'Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy'. It features a navigation menu with 'Home', 'Project', 'Consortium', 'Articles', 'News', 'Outcomes', 'Meetings', and 'Exhibitions'. A red arrow points from the 'Web Portal' label to the 'Meetings' tab. Below the navigation, there are sections for 'Latest meetings', 'Meetings > Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy', and 'RELATED ITEMS'. The 'RELATED ITEMS' section includes 'Deliverables', 'Documents', and 'Members'. The 'Documents' list includes various meeting reports and documents. The 'Members' list includes names like Martin Cobo, Angel Ozcelik-Guney, Sedef Tardini, Dr. Stefano Joklova, Dr. Viera Charalambous, Dr. Nadia Sentieri, Dr. Carla Pizzo Schwendener, Anna Roche, Jim Coms, Tomas Pao, Alexandra Pfiko, Dr. Heinrich Madrazo, Dr. Leandro Steina, Dr. Nicolai Diaconu, and Dr. Adriana. The right screenshot is the 'OIKONETWORK' dashboard for the same meeting. It features a navigation menu with 'Partners', 'Members', 'Workpackages', 'Deliverables', and 'Meetings'. A red arrow points from the 'OIKONETWORK' label to the 'Meetings' tab. The dashboard shows a 'VIEW: Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy' section with a list of meeting items. A red arrow points from the 'Meeting: "Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy"' label to a network graph visualization on the right side of the dashboard. The graph shows a central node for the meeting, connected to various other nodes representing related activities and documents. Below the graph, there is a 'Project Activities' section with a table of activities. A red arrow points from the 'Dashboard' label to the 'Project Activities' section. The table has columns for 'DATE', 'TYPE', and 'TITLE'. The activities listed include:

DATE	TYPE	TITLE
January 30, 2015	MI	Third meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy
November 04, 2014	CI	Deliverable 2.1 Readings on contemporary housing research
November 01, 2014	EV	Contemporary Living Patterns - Dublin
October 10, 2014	EV	Lisbon workshop prototypes
September 24, 2014	EV	Poster exhibition "Global Meeting"
July 11, 2014	CI	Deliverable 3.2 Video reporting of participatory actions
June 27, 2014	MI	Second meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy
June 16, 2014	MI	Second meeting of the subnetwork pedagogy

Figure 16. Multiple forms of visualization of the semantic data

5 INFORMATION VISUALIZATION TOOLS

The information introduced in the information system is visualized in two environments, Dashboard and Graph Search (OIKONETWORK). The information shown in each one has the same source: the semantically structured information introduced with the tools described in the previous chapter.

5.1 Dashboard

The Dashboard can be accessed at Home page of the web portal, selecting the “view as list” icon (Figure 17). It shows a list of the most recent information introduced in the semantic information system, structured by categories. The categories work as filters to select the information. A colour code helps to identify the items of the same category. Each element of the list has a link to OIKONETWORK, where the selected item is visualized as a node of the map.

Figure 17. Dashboard

5.2 Graph search (OIKONETWORK)

A visual graph tool has been created to enable access and navigation to the data semantically modelled, following the procedures described in the previous sections. The data that has been semantically modelled and displayed in the visual map includes:

- the project work programme, with its structure of work packages and deliverables
- the contents of the Google doc shared documents that partners used to report about their activities
- the table of research themes created to identify areas of collaboration among partners
- the information that is generated as the project progresses (news, meetings, reports, publications, etc.)

OIKONETWORK can be accessed from a direct link in the home page of OIKONET portal. Alternatively, the user can arrive to Oikonetwork navigating through the web pages. In this case, there are two possible links (Figure 18): 1. Clicking on the icon “W” associated to an information block and 2. Clicking on a related item. In both cases, the visual map is opened in a new window and the user can continue searching for the information in the visual map.

Figure 18. Links between web pages and Oikonetwork

5.2.1 Interface

The interface is divided in three windows (Figure 19): a submenu on the left side, the visual maps at the centre and the detailed information the nodes on the right side. The main menu sits on top of these three windows. The structure of this menu is consistent with the one of the menu on the web portal home page.

Figure 19. Structure of the interface

The main menu of Oikonetwork reflects the ontology of the information system created for the OIKONET project. It consists of the following entries:

- **Partners**, the organizations that are participating in the project
- **Members**, the persons working in the organizations that are part of the project
- **Workpackages**, the description of the work packages (contents, objectives, deliverables) as described in the work programme
- **Deliverables**, the reports and outputs to be produced according to the work programme
- **Activities**, works and actions taking place during the realization of the project
- **Workshops**, the three planned international workshops
- **Conferences**, the three planned international conferences
- **Meetings**, the biannual meetings planned for each of the three subnetworks
- **Exhibitions**, displays of the project outputs
- **News** generated during the project lifetime
- **Research issues** identified by the consortium, subdivided in themes and subthemes
- **Learning spaces**, collaborative learning activities carried out around a particular topic
- **Outcomes**, products resulting from the project activities

5.2.2 Navigation

Starting from the menu, the user can see the information which is associated to the selected item in the visual map (Figure 20). The information in the map, can be displayed using filters. By selecting a node in the map, it is possible to access to the detailed information associated to the selected node (files, descriptions) by selecting the option “View” (mouse over the node).

Figure 20. Navigation structure

To navigate through the network, the option “Focus” (mouse over the node) is used. This places the selected node at the centre and unfolds the related items. The number of levels than can be displayed at once has been limited to two, to avoid an excess of visual information.

5.2.3 Implementation

Oikonetwork has been implemented in PHP using the development framework CodeIgniter (www.codeigniter.com). The front-end interface has been implemented in HTML, CSS and Javascript. The visual map of Oikonetwork has been created with VivaGraphJS, a drawing library for Javascript. VivaGraphJS supports rendering graphs using WebGL and SVG.

The process for retrieving data elements from the semantic data repository is the following:

1. Oikonetwork invokes a method of the API
2. The API retrieves the data from the semantic data repository
3. The API encapsulates the data in JSON format and sends back the data to Oikonetwork
4. Oikonetwork decodes the JSON data and creates a data structure for VivaGraphJS.
5. Oikonetwork renders in the front-end interface using HTML, CSS, and Javascript.

An example of the data structure used by VivaGraphJS for creating the visual map:

```

array(
  [0] => array(
    ['gT'] => 'node'
    ['name'] => 566
    ['size'] => 15
    ['color'] => '#ff0000'
    ['type'] => 'Conference'
    ['isPinned'] => 'true'
    ['text'] => ...
    ['textNom'] => ...
    ['nodesRelation'] => array(
      [0] => array(
        ['uriId'] => 563
        ['type'] => 'Document'
        ['nameElement'] => 'OIKONET Conference Bratislava - Blog'
        ['subType'] =>
        ['shortTitle'] =>
      )
      [1] => array(... 5 elements ...)
      [2] => array(... 5 elements ...)
    )
  )
  [1] => array(... 9 elements ...)
  [2] => array(... 9 elements ...)
)

```

The array contains a list of items to display as a graph layout. Each item is a node with some parameters (e.g. name, size, type...) and relations to other nodes. With this information VivaGraphJS library can render the nodes and relations of the visual map.

6 FURTHER ENHANCEMENTS

During the second half of the project, a usability test of the OIKONET platform was prepared by USI and then carried out by partners. A total of 34 tests were completed from 27 partner institutions (see Appendices in Deliverable 5.1 “OIKONET Digital Platform”). As a result of this test, the menus were harmonized with those of the web portal. This way, the same navigation structure could be used in both environments (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Menu structure in the web portal and in Oikonetwork

In addition, a tutorial was created to explain users how to navigate in the visual graph and to make a proper use of the associative navigation mode to find out information about the project activities (Figures 22, 23).

Figure 22. Oikonetwork tutorial

Figure 23. Oikonetwork tutorial

7 CONCLUSIONS

The semantic data repository developed in this project has enabled the creation of a web portal which reflects the relational character of the network activities, by modelling the relationships between the different elements of information (project description, outcomes, activities, partners) in multiple ways. Since there was no technology available which could be easily adapted to fulfil the project requirements, it has been necessary to create a semantic data repository from scratch.

The repository provides the necessary flexibility to model the information in multiple ways. The process to feed the repository with information using the forms can be time consuming, but once the procedures are in place, it becomes relatively straightforward to introduce information in an associative way. Nevertheless, it requires an advanced user to take care of inserting the information in the right way using the forms created before by an expert user.

The interrelationships of the information introduced in the system are visualized in two environments: in the web portal and in the visual map. The consistency between the menu structure of the two environments facilitates the navigation across them, in both directions. However, direct links between the information contained in the two environments are unidirectional, from the web portal onto the visual map.